

ADP - SOCIAL SCIENCE DATA ARCHIVES

Analyze data! Deposit study! Promote science!

Supporting public opinion researchers to make their work transparent

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WAPOR 2022, 10-13.11.2022, Dubai

Slovenian Social Science Data Archives

- Founded in 1997
- Slovenian **national research data centre** for social sciences
- **Member of CESSDA** ERIC since 2017
- Status of a **trust-worthy archive** (CoreTrustSeal since 2018)
- involved in EU and national projects
- holds more than 650 studies

- Members (22) / Observers (1)
- Partners (12)

1976, Amsterdam
ZA, UKDA, DDA, Steinmetz,
BASS, NSD, ADPSS

2014, Launch of ESFRI Roadmap 2016
update process

CESSDA on ESFRI Landmarks

June 14th 2017,
CESSDA-ERIC

CESSDA - Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives

*" Member countries seek to **increase the scientific excellence and efficacy of European research in the social sciences**, as well as to expand easy access to data and metadata regardless of borders. They want to provide a research infrastructure for their researchers, and join forces among their (national) data service providers."*

Key tasks:

- ◊ Developing **standards and best practices** around the management and archiving of social science data.
- ◊ **Facilitating access** to important data resources.
- ◊ **Developing tools, training and co-ordinating network.**

<https://www.cessda.eu/>

What is research data...

... primary sources that underpin scientific research and enable derivation of theoretical or applied findings.

([Preparing research data for open access : guide for data producers](#), 2015)

The tangible forms this 'material' may take are e.g. "*facts, observations, interviews, recordings, measurements, experiments, simulations, and software; numerical, descriptive and visual; raw, cleaned up and processed*" (Van Berchum & Grootveld, 2017).

INFORMATION TYPES

I'll make my work transparent by following FAIR principles.

The ultimate goal of **FAIR** is to optimise the reuse of data.

Research data management

... refers to how you *handle, organise, and structure* your research data throughout the research process.

COSTING TOOL

... addresses also your plans for the data *after* the research is complete.

The HE Model Grant Agreement requires that a data management plan ('DMP') is established and regularly updated.

CESSDA Training Team (2017 - 2020). *CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide*. Bergen, Norway: CESSDA ERIC. Retrieved from <https://dmeg.cessda.eu/>

DATA Publication

PUBLICATIONS AND DATA

It is expected that a Data Publication will ensure that data will potentially be considered as a first-class research output (Knowledge Exchange, 2013).

For a dataset to “count” as a publication should be:

- Properly documented with metadata;
- **Reviewed for quality;**
- Searchable and discoverable in catalogues (or databases);
- Citable in articles.

Where to publish?

⊕ Journal supplementary material service

⊕ Institutional data repository

⊕ General purpose repository

zenodo

⊕ Domain specific data repository

 DARIAH-SI

⊕ Trusted domain specific data repository

 cessda

CLARIN.SI

re3data.org
REGISTRY OF RESEARCH DATA REPOSITORIES

Journals & open data policies

More and more journals are demanding data availability statements

PLOS journals require authors to **make all data necessary to replicate their study's findings publicly available without restriction at the time of publication.** When specific legal or ethical restrictions prohibit public sharing of a data set, authors must indicate how others may obtain access to the data.

<https://journals.plos.org/plosone/s/data-availability>)

Are there data associated with the article you're submitting to a Taylor & Francis journal? Over 2,000 Taylor & Francis journals have **policies which state how these data should be shared.** The details below will help you get to grips with the policies and the steps you'll need to take.

(<https://authorservices.taylorandfrancis.com/data-sharing-policies/>)

Journals & open data policies

Research Data Policy Types at Springer: Data sharing and data citation is encouraged; Data sharing and evidence of data sharing encouraged; **Data sharing encouraged and statements of data availability required; Data sharing, evidence of data sharing and peer review of data required** (<https://www.springernature.com/la/authors/research-data-policy/data-policy-types/12327096>)

Availability of materials and data at the *Humanities and Social Science Communications*

An inherent principle of publication is that others should be able to replicate and build upon the authors' published claims. **Therefore, a condition of publication is that authors are required to make materials, data and associated protocols promptly available to readers without undue qualifications. Any restrictions on the availability of materials or information must be disclosed to the publishing team at the time of submission.***Humanities and Social Science Communications* (see [Editorial policies](#))

Introduction to TOP Guidelines

	0	1	2	3
Data citation	No mention of data citation.	Journal describes citation of data in guidelines to authors	Article requires appropriate citation for data and materials used	Article is not published until providing appropriate citation for

Data transparency	Data sharing is encouraged, or not mentioned	Articles must state whether or not data are available.	Articles must have publicly available data, or an explanation why ethical or legal constraints prevent it.	Articles must have publicly available data and must be used to computationally reproduce or confirm results prior to publication
Details	Level 0 applies if the journal policy does not cover all of the underlying data reported in an article.	Requiring a data availability statement satisfies this level.	<p>If the journal only requires some data to be preserved, e.g. proteomics, then this level is not reached. If the article must include an availability statement for all other data, then level 1 is reached, else level 0.</p> <p>If the policy strongly encourages data sharing, this level is not reached.</p> <p>Policies that require sharing with editors and reviewers only do not apply.</p> <p>Policies that require sharing only "upon request" do not apply.</p> <p>Words such as "should" or "expect" may be ambiguous. Typically, "should" implies an encouragement and not a requirement. "Expects" suggests a requirement, but clarification may be needed.</p>	Policy must cover transparency and sharing requirements of level 2, plus include a computational reproducibility step.

words such as "should" or "expect" may be ambiguous. Typically, "should" implies an encouragement and not a requirement. "Expects" suggests a requirement, but clarification may be needed.

Full Rubriq with examples is here <https://osf.io/t2yu5/>

Support

GESIS: up to May 2022: 57

replication

packages linked to articles (data,
code, supplements)

To journals with designing comprehensive, thorough, and clear **data sharing policies**, suitable for the social sciences.

To authors for handling the **data archiving process**, including metadata, contextual info, replication files etc.

Research Data Management training for authors and researchers towards archiving and sharing data, incl. data citation.

Services Supporting Research

Training

Learn how to discover, use, manage and preserve research data

Upcoming Events

Tue 6 Sep 2022

Dataverse train-the-trainer event in September
In September, DANS will be organising a train-the-trainer event on using Dataverse as an archiv...

Thu 15 Sep 2022

New Data Types in Data Management and Archiving

New Data Types in Data Management and Archiving workshop will focus on the management, archivin...

Event Calendar

Featured Resources

The [Data Management Expert Guide](#) (DMEG) is a comprehensive guide to Research Data Management and FAIR data principles.

Data Management Expert Guide

The [Data Archiving Guide](#) (DAG) is designed to provide new employees at social science data archives with a general understanding of the work a data archive performs.

Data Archiving Guide

Trust and Standards

Each national Service Provider works towards achieving the Trustworthy Digital Repository (TDR) standard selected by CESSDA: the [CoreTrustSeal](#).

The CoreTrustSeal defines repository requirements in terms of organisational infrastructure, digital object management, technology and security. Trust is essential between CESSDA Service Providers and with their data depositors and users.

Since CESSDA selected the internationally recognised CoreTrustSeal it has been acknowledged as important for enabling FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data and has become the recommended certification approach for data repositories within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

CESSDA Digital Tools

CESSDA Data Catalogue

Search tens of thousands of social science research studies from our European Service Providers.

ELSST Thesaurus

The European Language Social Science Thesaurus is a broad-based multilingual thesaurus for the social sciences.

European Question Bank

The EQB is a cross-national question bank for social science and humanities research.

Vocabulary Service

Search, browse and download controlled vocabularies in a variety of languages.

Resource Directory

Access resources for data archives and data professionals from CESSDA, its Service Providers and partners.

Metadata Validator

Validate metadata for compatibility with the CESSDA Data Catalogue and the European Question Bank.

Three CESSDA Roadshow event posters are displayed. The top poster is for 'Roadshow on COVID-19' on 30 September 2021, 14:00-16:00 CEST, with a 'SAVE THE DATE' button. The middle poster is for 'Roadshow on migration' on 08 October 2021, 14:00 CEST, also with a 'SAVE THE DATE' button. The bottom poster is for 'Roadshow on Cancer and Chronic Diseases' on 21 October 2021, 14:00-15:30 CEST and 13:00-14:30 BST, with a 'SAVE THE DATE' button. Each poster features the CESSDA logo and a list of speakers.

BY [Saif Shneyin](#) for LIBER 2022

DO NOT BE SO 2014

SHARE!

DATA

AMF.

www.msgery.com / www.aukeherrema.nl

RDA FOURTH PLENARY MEETING

IF YOU HAVE ANY FURTHER QUESTIONS...

... CONTACT ADP

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Faculty of Social Sciences
Social Science Data Archive
Kardeljeva ploščad 5
1000 Ljubljana
Slovenia

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 arhiv.podatkov@fdv.uni-lj.si

 [Arhiv.Druzboslovnih.Podatkov](https://www.facebook.com/Arhiv.Druzboslovnih.Podatkov)

 [@ArhivPodatkov](https://twitter.com/ArhivPodatkov)

Sources

CESSDA Training Team (2017 - 2020). *CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide*. Bergen, Norway: CESSDA ERIC. Retrieved from <https://dmeg.cessda.eu/>

Štebe, Janez, Bezjak, Sonja, Alvanides, Serafeim, Recker, Jonas, Glavica, Marijana, Kranjec, Irena, Laaksonen, Helena, Kondyli, Dimitra, Klironomos, Nicolas, Linardis, Apostolos, & Kleiner, Brian. (2022, June 9). The CESSDA Data Archives joint efforts to support journals in data sharing and reproducibility [Panel]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6683796>

Bezjak, Sonja, Masten, Sergeja, Glavica, Marijana, Vlašiček, Denis, Ramthun, Roland, Doorn, Peter, Breure, Leen, Recker, Jonas, Heuberger, Simon, & Cannon, Matt. (2021, November 11). Making Social Science Research Transparent [Webinar]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5719323>

Want to test your knowledge

CESSDA Quiz: www.cessda.eu/dmeg

Take the quiz below and find out which chapters of DMEG will be most useful for you.

Take the DMEG quiz

LoD Data Management Challenge game: <https://lod.sshopencloud.eu>

Using Administrative Data for Research

SOCIAL MEDIA AND RESEARCH

